

FULL AUTOMATION OF REAL-TIME PROCESSES IN INTERACTIVE COMPOSITIONS: TWO RELATED EXAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyses two interactive compositions of my own authorship: both include live instruments and a fully automated programming of live electronics using MAX. On the one hand, the paper introduces *Intersections (memories)* for clarinet in Bb, (2007/8); on the other hand, a comparison is offered, about how *Confluences (Rainbows II)* for flute, clarinet, violin, cello and piano (2010/12), is an amplification of the former piece with regard to not only its compositional further development, but also as a much more complex case of full automated live-electronics. The subject of full automation, including a historical perspective is explained in an article by the author in 2010 [1]. From a purely compositional perspective, both works share also a similar type of music dramaturgy due to their common *something to hold on to factors (STHotF)*, as described by Landy [2], and later, also by Weale [3]. Hence, the *poiesis* and *aesthesis* [4] of both compositions are also hereby shortly introduced, to shed more light about the reasons for the full automation of their electronic parts, as these two aspects are solidly united to the electronics used and their relationship to the intended dramaturgy embedded in the two works.

1. INTRODUCTION

This article explains the technical and compositional facts that surround the pieces *Intersections (memories)* for clarinet in Bb, from the years 2007/8 and *Confluences (Rainbows II)* for quintet (flute, clarinet, violin, cello and piano) from 2010/12, both compositions by the author of this paper. The latter composition is actually an amplification of the first piece, with several changes in the instrumentation, composition and electronics, although the main core structure of the original piece is maintained.

The main reason for the utilisation of complete automation of the live-electronics processes in both pieces rely upon the facts already explained in a former article of my authorship, *Raising Awareness About Complete Automation of Live-Electronics: a Historical Perspective* [1], and I would refer the reader to that article for full details. Herewith enunciated however, the main reasons therein exposed, which demonstrate

clear advantages in the usage of fully automated live-electronics:

- a. Concentration and reduction of unnecessary activities during the performance, allowing the performer or performers to purely concentrate on the musical aspects of the performance.
- b. Relative independence of the electronics from the composer's presence during the performance, as the live electronics do not need further manipulation during the performance, just to be activated at the start of the piece.
- c. Better combination of processes and lesser risks during the actual performance, as full automation allows for accurate and more complex combinations of different real-time processes such as multiple textures made of several simultaneous layers of real-time DSP functions, which are rather limited in those cases in which only manual manipulation is applied during a performance.
- d. Principal means for the synchronisation is the usage of time-code (SMTPE) to follow events specified with an exact time position on the music score with the help of a SMPTE display on the stage (and eventually, a mirror of SMPTE times on the computer).
- e. Accurate synchronisation of events and processes at the time of performing the pieces such as, for example, an accurate recording of a specific music motive or melody. A typical example of this case the case can be found in the first bar of *Confluences (Rainbows II)*.
- f. Effective way of testing electronics beforehand: if the different DSP functions run steadily at the exact same set-times, they can be entirely tested while the work is being programmed and composed, resulting in less, or even no danger of exceeding, for example, CPU's or memory limits, as the real-time electronics can be fully monitored beforehand.
- g. Frequent distribution of interactive pieces for performance purpose: thanks to the evolution of computing technology since the 1990s, pieces using full automation of their live-electronics have the advantage of an easier, costless, more effective and more frequent distribution, as the only requirements for their performance are the score and the patch/software. These advantages have also a beneficial impact on rehearsals and their organisation, as the full automation should normally allow for faster set-up times as well as faster rehearsal times.

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In spite of the fact, that there are minor disadvantages in the usage of full-automated live-electronics, which are referred to in full in the article alluded to above [1], I shall not develop on them herewith, as they are not relevant to this article.

It is however important to stress upon the absolute accuracy of the programming required for a fully automated electronic part. Although this is already the case for *Intersections (memories)*, the addition of four more instruments in *Confluences (Rainbows II)*, turns the programming of the electronics into a much more complex process, in the particular case of this piece, with a total of more than 1000 function calls. Both compositions include several different types of DSP processes for a constant output in 5.1 surround image, such as surround diffusion, different types granulation, pitch shifting, several reverberation effects (including a variation of the Schroeder reverberation), spectral multiplication (convolution), pitch recognition, ring modulation of comb filtered sources and several recordings of each of the instruments into separate buffers for further manipulation during the performance.

Both compositions follow the same pattern for the writing of the general score: there is one staff for each instrument, another staff for the SMPTE times and a final staff, reserved to described the DSP functions occurring at precise times in the live-electronics part. Figures 1 and 3 below show examples of this in *Intersections*. The inclusion of the description of DSP functions in the score is meant hereby for information purposes only, as, due to the full automation of those processes, such indications are not needed for the performance of the piece to take place.

In order to finish this introduction, it is also worth mentioning, that the programming of the automatic real-time processes is absolutely entwined with the intended dramaturgy embedded in the pieces, and therefore, it must be seen as an essential and indissoluble component of the compositional process, as it is explained in section 2 below.

2. DRAMATURGY AND COMPOSITIONAL TECHNIQUES IN BOTH COMPOSITIONS

Revisiting the last topic of the former section, it must be stated upfront, that the composition processes in both works –and therefore their full dramatic content (as it is also the case in any other work of my authorship)– are conceived as a full unity, in which the full automation of the real-time processes does not only offer all of the advantages mentioned above, but also, that the absolute accuracy of them happening in exactly the way they have been programmed/composed is a constitutive part of the intended dramaturgy, notwithstanding the type of electronic DSP functions used in each particular case.

Although different similar meanings to the verb ‘intersect’ can be found in English, the title of the first

piece indicates *something sharing a common area*.¹ The composition has its origin in a secret story, which is therefore not immediately apparent to the listener: there are three musical motives representing two different characters, all of which interact with one another forming new motives by intersecting at different points of the piece, with the results still sharing the original materials (their genetic identity) of each one in these combinations. Two of these motives represent the first character, the first one being of predominantly melodic nature, constituted by the pitches A, B, B, B \flat , A and Eb, whilst the second motive for this character is purely rhythmical. The second character is represented by only one motive, which includes rhythmic and melodic attributes.

The story is based upon a real life experience of human relationship of a love affair, thus the reason for the two characters with their own motives and the transformations acting upon each other through time, forming in some cases, –as displayed in figure 4 later in this section– a new unity by the merge of those motives *intersecting* with one another. The three motives for the two characters can be found in figures 1 to 3.

Figure 1. First character: motive No 1 (melodic)

Figure 2. First character motive No 2 (rhythmic)

Figure 3. Second character motive

¹ 'Intersect: to share a common area'. (<http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/intersect>)

There is also a third character, which appears transformed at different times during the piece. One of the most important of these transformations is the dissection of this third character melody into its constitutive notes, played isolated by the clarinet at different moments, each of which is recorded separately and individually by the electronics into a cumulative buffer; toward the end of the piece, this motive is played for the first time in its original full form only by the electronics, with the addition of granular synthesis, revealing the first Leitmotiv from the opera *Parsifal* by Richard Wagner (*Liebesmotiv*)². This is one of the several examples in these two pieces of the *indissoluble* relationship during the composition process between writing the music and programming the full automated electronic. In this case, such a cumulative buffer adds events that are played across the first and middle parts of the piece, merging them together in order to play Wagner's melody in full length and in granulated form (bar 49 of the score). Without the accuracy of full automation, examples such as the one just explained, which require the full reconstruction of 18 separate recordings into one single melodic motive, would be difficult or even impossible to achieve with the precision required by its dramatic intention.

The musical motives cannot be taken as significant *STHotFs* for this piece though, as they are not evident to the listener, although the constant repetition and transformation (and intersections) of these three elements (the Leitmotiv and the two musical characters) may allow for the listener to perceive them in a rather recursive manner, becoming increasingly familiar with them during the performance of the piece. For those listeners familiar with Wagner's work, the Leitmotiv included herein should be a strong point of reference with regard to the dramaturgic intention of the piece though.

Following the idea of an *act of merging*,³ *Confluences (Rainbows II)* keeps the main dramatic core of the clarinet piece, but enhances it not only with the addition of four new instruments, but also with the amplification of the motivic textures highly enriched by a rather complex programming of real-time DSP functions in the live-electronics part, as it is explained in full detail in the next section. In this piece, the *Parsifal* motive is removed from the piece, one of several issues that insure that, in spite of the shared core, the two works should be listened to as separate and individual entities. As it can be gathered from the above, in both cases, the most significant *STHotF* is the title of each of the compositions, mostly the first word, although the second word helps to give an idea of what else can be expected.⁴ The love story suggested in the first piece is replaced by the confluence of several 'voices' of those characters in the second, which, possessing different timbres (due to the richer instrumentation), form a much

more complex net or context, rather than the sole existence of two main characters and what unifies them (Wagner's Leitmotiv) intersecting with one another, as in the first composition.

According to another article of my authorship [5], based upon the concept of *Intention/Reception* in music by Weale and Landy [3], I amplified the *intention* and *reception* aspects of music dramaturgy by adding subcategories to both of them. The intention, called therein *Intrinsic Dramaturgy* [5], is divided into two subgroups: *a-priori* and *a-posteriori*. The first subgroup –*a-priori*– includes those works in which the dramatic elements of the piece are known beforehand by the listener, such as, for example, in the case of an opera or due to the text of a song.⁵ The second subgroup –*a-posteriori*– includes those pieces where the dramatic element is not evident to the listener, and therefore additional information (such as *STHotFs*) is required for a minimal understanding of the intended dramatic plot. *The two pieces herein explained belong to this second subcategory of Intrinsic Dramaturgy.*

From the point of view of the instrumental techniques utilised, although more obvious in the clarinet piece, the two compositions rely mostly on the usage of advanced techniques, many of which are conceived in order to blend with the programmed electronics. The most common techniques utilised are: micro-intervallic; multiphonics (including multiphonic-trills); toneless articulation (woodwind instruments); key strokes; toneless playing (blowing through the clarinet, with an embouchure not enough to produce the fingered normal pitch); slap-tongue notes; playing notes with teeth on the reed of the clarinet with flutter tongue (which should produce a high pitch whistling sound); very fast tremolo over all 4 strings at the same time (for violin and cello, as in Berio's *Sequenza VI* for viola); playing with the hair of the bow on the side of the bridge of the cello, and so forth.⁶

Figure 4 shows not only an example of some these techniques for the clarinet in bars 29 and 30 in *Intersections*, but also the intersections of the three main motives of the two characters into one single motive in bar 29.

Figure 4. Example of advanced techniques (both bars) including and intersection of motives in *Intersections* in bar 29.

3. REAL-TIME DSP IN BOTH COMPOSITIONS – USE OF FULL

² Love motive.

³ Confluence: 'a coming or flowing together, meeting, or gathering at one point'.

(<http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/confluence>)

⁴ This, of course, without mentioning, that a possible program note in a concert could make the idea clearer to the listener.

⁵ I thereafter divide this subcategory into three further subgroups: stage drama, non-stage drama and preconceived musical forms.

⁶ A full description of these techniques is offered in each of the scores of these two compositions.

AUTOMATION IN THE PROGRAMMING OF THE 2 WORKS

The main reasons for the usage of full automation in these two compositions have been already explained in the former sections, hence, this section is dedicated to the explanation of how the fully automated electronics work, with a description of some of the DSP functions involved and how the automation in each case proves extremely useful for both dramatic and musical purposes.

However, before discussing some of those processes, a general description of how the full automation works in both cases must be introduced.

The two pieces were composed and programmed in order to completely avoid any type of extra-musical activity on the stage for the solely purpose of activating the electronics, such as pressing pedals or keys, manipulation of faders and so on during the performance. Hence, the audience can concentrate on the music played by the instrumentalist eliminating in this manner distraction or even loss of interest (avoiding therefore Delalande's sixth listening behaviour [6])⁷ caused by extra activities on the stage not related with playing a musical instrument. With regard to the dramaturgic aspect of this, it is my goal, that the performance of this type of pieces must create an environment allowing listeners for a full concentration on sound, mostly on its morphological, dramaturgical and spatial aspects.

In order to achieve that set of goals in these pieces, the computer is not on the stage, but with a second person (normally the composer) sitting at the mixing desk. The only device required on the stage is a SMPTE⁸ display, showing the time-code send by MAX, which permits the player to follow it while reading the score of the piece.⁹ The MAX patch begins by pressing a 'start' button (sending a MAX 'bang') and from then onwards, *no further manipulation on the computer is necessary*. The MAX patch is provided its own full score¹⁰, in which each and every DSP function is thereafter automatically started, as a chain reaction to the initial 'bang'. After the start point is activated, there are fifteen seconds (beginning by SMPTE 23:59:45:00) before the piece begins, which give more than enough time to the musician/s to prepare for the performance. Thus, any DSP function programmed for the composition starts at SMPTE 00:00:00:00, the actual start of the piece.

The person in charge of activation the live-electronics and balancing the overall sound via the mixing desk (normally the composer, but, as indicated before, full

automation allows for anyone to perform this role) is required only to follow the SMPTE on the MAX main patch (a mirror of what is being sent to the SMPTE display) and concentrate purely on the input and output levels on the mixing console, in order to achieve the best possible sound balance inside the concert hall. Hence, automation allows here potentially for an optimal overall sound result, as the focus is on the sound balance during the performance, and not on the activation of several DSP functions.

Having said that, this section continues with a description of some of the DSP functions utilised in the pieces, with a fair amount of detail about how they were programmed and an explanation about how full automation is invaluable for an overall satisfactory performance of these two compositions.

3.1 – Surround sound (5.1)

Both compositions have a final output of a typical 5.1 Surround sound (L, C, R, SR, SL and LFE¹¹). The LFE becomes the signal of all other channels via a *low-pass* filter with a cut-off frequency of 120 Hz although it can too, if required, process its own, independent low frequency signal.

The panning system between the 5 loudspeakers is programmed with an automatic combination of algorithms, which can either (a) maintain a constant time in the panning speed or (b) constantly change the time of circulation of sound between the speakers using a linear function between two given durations (in milliseconds): the start and end *inter-speaker-times*. The panning movement can be programmed in two directions: clockwise and anticlockwise. A third option is the random selection of one loudspeaker at a time, with the same options for time manipulation formerly explained (*a* and *b*) in this paragraph.

It should be made clear to the reader, that surround panning (despite the inclusion of joysticks in some advanced digital mixers such as the Yamaha DM2000, which offer some flexibility in the matter) is rather difficult to be manually controlled when several and simultaneous events are at work. Thus, automation is a solid and flexible option to obtain a constant speed between changing speakers, especially in cases of very short *inter-speaker-times*, which are impossible to be reproduced manually due to their short duration. The advantage of automation offers herewith the following options:

- *effective and full control of the panning speed*: the constant change of *inter-speaker-times* can be controlled from fast to slow or vice-versa (or even be left at a fixed rate), whilst very fast panning movements of less than 150 milliseconds produce a spatial granulation of the diffused sounds;
- *control of the panning direction*: clockwise, anticlockwise or random;
- *increase and decrease of panning speed*: by controlling the panning speed, imperceptible changes

⁷ Delalande categorised the listening experience in six different behaviours, where the sixth is called 'non-listening behaviour'.

⁸ The SMPTE is read by MAX in a subpatch, which contains the byphase modulated signal already recorded in an AIFF audio file. The output of the audio file comes out of the audio interface from a 7th channel and enters the SMPTE display on the stage, which decodes the information of the audio byphase modulated signal.

⁹ See figures 1, 2 and 3, which shows examples how the musical score is written.

¹⁰ The score in MAX consists of different timelines, which trigger each DSP function at the given time in the general music score.

¹¹ LFE is the short version of *Low Frequency Effect*, basically the signal sent to the subwoofer of the 5.1 system.

- in the panning speed can be introduced, which respond in absolute accuracy to the parameters programmed;
- the already mentioned *avoidance of manual surround panning*, which is rather unpredictable and not always possible.
- *smooth and constant change of channel/speaker* in the surround panning, by the addition fade-in/fade-out envelopes for each channel, which make a constant crossover at any change of channel, whether clockwise or anti-clockwise or in random motion.

Particularly for the two pieces explained in this paper, the implementation of the surround sound and therefore, of the surround image in 5.1 is rather different in each case: while in *Intersections*, the surround movement and image is only at the end of the output chain, just before reaching the *DAC*, *Confluences* is so programmed, that several of the DSP functions in the MAX patch, such as pitch-shifting, ring modulation of comb filtered signals, multiple sample playback, and spectral multiplication (convolution), all possess their *own* individual surround options, which can be played simultaneously, therefore creating a texture of different surround/panning layers with different panning speeds within the general 5.1 image. This is impossible to be achieved without the aid of a fully automated programmed panning system. Figure 5 below, shows and example of the pitch-shifting function in *Confluences*.

Figure 5. Automatic panning in 5.1 surround sound sub-patch (MAX 5) in *Confluences (Rainbows II)*

The results of this MAX sub-patch are sent subsequently directly to the general 5.1 output in the main patch. The main dramatic reason for the presence of surround textures, as explained above for *Confluences*, is the amplification of the environment in which the five different instruments develop their dramatic network of different combinations of the main motives, showing different aspects, which are not intended to be exposed in such a way in *Intersections*.

3.2 - The usage of a cumulative buffer in 'Intersections (memories)' for sample playback

This case applies only to the former piece, and not only depends on full automation, but also the precision

required herewith cannot be achieved by any other means. Parsifal's *Liebesmotiv* (as described by Kurt Pahlen [7]) is the first to appear in the Overture of Wagner's work. It is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. *Liebesmotiv* from the opera *Parsifal*, by Wagner. The numbers below each note indicate the duration of each note in quavers, which are translated into seconds in MAX for a cumulative buffer made of single recordings of each note during the performance.

In order to be able to record all of these notes in the right order and duration, each of the pitches from this melody needed to be composed within *Intersections*, not only with regard to their individual duration, but also taking under consideration, that the dynamic (amplitude level) of each note had to be as similar as possible to allow for a full playback of the Leitmotiv by the computer alone. Each time one of these notes is played at different moments between SMPTE: 00:02:10:00 and 00:08:17:00, the clarinet is accompanied only by a smooth reverberation of each note, which accentuates its intended dramatic meaning by extending its duration in time and at the same time, in the space.

MAX allows for a cumulative buffer to be used, which, from a first sample, recorded at the start of the buffer, all of the other notes are appended one after the other. In this way, a forty-five seconds long buffer is finished after 18 samples have been recorded (the final sample is recorded in bar 48, at SMPTE: 00:08:17:00), shortly afterwards, at SMPTE: 00:08:35:00, the electronics play it alone and repeatedly in full duration, granulating each note in a circular surround panning.

The required precision for the recording of each note, so that the duration and the sound of each note are recorded, was only possible by the implementation of full automation in MAX: while the clarinetist has only to follow the SMPTE displayed on the stage in order to play the notes accurately on the given time and without having to care about the activation of each recording (and therefore, allowing for a maximum in concentration on how to play those tender notes, marked always *mf* and *dolce* in the score), the electronics record and append each note/sample automatically into the buffer, adding in the process a short fade-in and fade-out of 195 milliseconds, in order to avoid clicks. Hence, the dramatic intention of playing the Leitmotiv in its complete and original form toward the end of *Intersections* is completely fulfilled, something which may not be possible if automation is not utilised. At this particular point, the musical score gives a very strong *STHotF*, by quoting Kurt Pahlen's words [7] at bar 49.¹²

¹² "Das erste Motiv ... bedeutet ... eine höhere, sublimierte Liebe, die durch eine Vereinigung mit Gott ihre Erfüllung erfährt." Translated freely into English: "The first motive ... means ... a higher, sublime love, which experiences its fulfillment through its union with God".

3.3 – Dynamic delays

The usage of this type of delays is already a common issue in several pieces I composed before these two. Although each piece uses them in different ways, the main idea of this DSP function is to produce delays across the 5.1 diffusion system, which, normally from the front to the rear, delay the sound by a random amount of time, which is herewith given in samples, and therefore dependant on the actual sampling rate for their actual time in ms¹³. The amplitude of each delay in the chain decreases (between 10% and 15% each time), and the algorithm works in such a way that, in spite of the random time selected by each activation of the patch, the second delay will always be longer than the first, the third longer than the second, and so forth. The output of each delay is sent thereafter to an individual reverb unit (slightly different for each of the five outputs) and further sent to a fixed output in the 5.1 surround image. Hence, this process is not included in any surround movement, as the surround image is fixed. Figure 7 shows the interior of this patch.

Figure 7. *Dynamic Delays* sub-patch in MAX, showing the calculation of each delay time in samples, the decrease of each subsequent delay in amplitude and the five individual outputs, corresponding to the 5.0 surround image. The smooth envelopes just before the output are there (*line~* objects) in order to avoid possible clicks.

Again, as shown in the former examples, this type of DSP function requires a level of precision in its activation, calculation and diffusion, which can only be achieved completely satisfactorily with the usage of full automation.

The intended dramaturgy embedded in this effect is to emphasise the second word of the title of the composition: *memories*, which seem to fade away with each repetition, as time passes by.

3.4 – Real Time Random Granulation using Pitch-Tracking and Phase modulation

The *Real Time Random Granulation* utilised herewith is a complex process which includes phase modulation in one of the three granular generators, whilst the overall grain generation depends on the incoming microphone signal(s) (from the live instruments), which is/are pitch-tracked by a pitch-recognition algorithm (external *fiddle~* object in MAX).

The granulation occurs between the interaction (ring modulation) of the incoming microphone signal and the sum of three cosine oscillators. These three oscillators are combined in such a manner, that the first receives the actual pitch value from the microphone signal from the pitch-tracker, while the second receives the same information, but this time multiplied by factor 2.5; the third oscillator receives its frequency input information directly from the output of oscillator No 2. All of these three oscillators are additionally phase modulated by the microphone signal. The output of the addition of these three oscillators is thereafter ring modulated with the incoming microphone signal, before being sent to the grain envelope generator, which calculates not only the *grain time*, but also the *inter-grain times*. Before the grains are sent to their output, they are filtered by a filter bank (the MAX object *svf~*), a combination of *low-pass* + *notch* + *high-pass* + *band-pass* filters, and then sent to a stereo output via delays (so that each channel has its own grain) and also to a reverb unit, with the purpose of adding some final colour to the overall sound. The reason for the stereo output from this patch, is that this granulation has the musical function of a rather established cloud within the surround image. Hence, the signal from each of the two channels is diffused only in quadrophony, in a crossing stereo image between the loudspeakers pairs L, R and SR, SL.

Thus, grains are a combination of multiple events, in which their frequency is mainly determined by the incoming frequency played by the live instruments, while the colour of the grains is mainly affected by the phase modulation and afterwards, by the ring modulation, whilst the filters add to the colour and create a certain illusion of multiple grain voices. The grain shape is a Gaussian-like envelope stored in a buffer, which also includes the *inter-grain time*.

It must be said though, that the last part of the chain, including the filter-bank, the delays and the final reverb were added for *Confluences*, while in *Intersections*, these features are missing (except for the filter-bank, which is nevertheless reduced to only a *low-pass* and a *notch* filter). In both cases however, the effect is of a smooth cloud of isolated grains appearing at each time in which there is an impulse coming from the live instrument(s). In *Confluences*, this type of granulation appears for the first time in bar 43, at SMPTE 00:06:03:00, triggered by the signals of the violin and the cello, whilst in *Intersections*, the first appearance is at SMPTE 00:01:17:00. Automation helps herewith for accurately switching on and off this DSP function at very exact moments without further notice. The sound-cloud formed by this specific type of granulation creates

¹³ Both pieces use a 44.1 kHz sampling rate, and therefore, the number of samples shown in Fig. 7 for each delay correspond to that rate. For example, the first delay showing a random calculation of 8548 samples, is, at a SR of 44.1 Khz, ca. 194 ms. long.

a rather ethereal atmosphere, which helps to underline the main dramatic ideas set by the music played by the instruments at those precise instances.

Figure 8 below shows the sub-patch for this type of granulation.

Figure 8. Real Time Random Granulation sub-patch in MAX. Most of the processes described above can be recognised in this figure. The pitch-tracking algorithm however is not included herewith, as it is an external sub-patch placed just before this one.

3.5 – Special Reverb Design for ‘Confluences (Rainbows II)’

A special reverb was specially programmed for *Confluences*.

Although the main schema of the utilisation of a chain of *all-pass* filters (see Figure 9 below) for the reverb model is applied herewith –in a similar way as used in the Schroeder reverb, a combination of *comb* filters followed by a chain or normally five *all-pass* filters– there are special differences compared to the original Schroeder model. These differences are mostly evident in the lack of *comb* filters at the start of the chain, which creates a slightly different reverb effect, but far from the tap effect, which was sought to be avoided herewith.

The reverb design for *Confluences* is made of eight *all-pass* filters, which are accessed by the original signal at once *and* in chain, with in some cases, feedback on some of the filters (between filter 4 and 1, see Figure 9). The result is a rather smooth and natural reverb, due to the fact that *all-pass* filters transmit all frequencies of steady state signal equally well [8]; therefore the amplitude response is 1 at each frequency, while the phase response, which determines the delay versus frequency, can be arbitrary, as Smith states [9].

In *Intersections*, on the other hand, only *taps* with feedback –basically *comb* filters without the *feed-forward* property of *all-pass* filters– are used, which result in frequency cancellations which, in spite of being in a position to imitate rather closely room effects, they can also yield ringing and instability, and therefore, are unfortunately not as satisfactory as the system described above.

Figure 9. Reverb system in *Confluences*, made of eight *all-pass* filters.

In both pieces however, reverb is used for the dramatic purpose of creating a special environment independent from the natural reverberation of the eventual venue. In particular, reverb is used herewith to keep the sound of the instrument(s) in the concert space longer after the player(s) have ceased to play those notes. In this manner, those sounds are projected into the 5.1 surround image independently from their original source, particularly in *Intersections*, alluding to the ‘memories’ in the title. As the special reverb design for *Confluences* was only programmed in 2012, it is possible, that *Intersections* will use it too in future performances, due to its obvious advantages, most compatible with its dramaturgic intention rather than the *taps* with feedback of the original version.

As the reverb parameters change throughout the length of both pieces, there is the constant danger of feedback occurring during the performance. Despite a fixed input value for each of the different microphones given automatically within the MAX patch in both compositions, there is still the need for additional manual level control during the performance from the mixing desk in order to avoid feedback, which is the only exception of automation for both pieces.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this article –as it was in my former writings about the topic of full automation of live electronics [1]– is, on the one hand the fact that applying complete automation to the real-time processes of the electronics of a piece of music has a tangible beneficial impact on the performance of interactive works as much as on the achievement of their dramaturgical intentions; and, on the other hand, there is also an evident beneficial impact on the rehearsal of such pieces and on their eased circulation in different venues. Herewith, the usage of full automation of DSP functions is described extensively through the comparison between two different practical examples.

This article shows also the required progression of the complexity embedded in this type of programming between a solo and an ensemble piece: *Confluences (Rainbows II)* is up to date the most complex example

of automation of live-electronics in my production. As demonstrated in those examples in section 3, several and simultaneous complex DSP processes were programmed in both compositions with no restrictions apart from those given by the CPU performance (and/or memory capacity) of the computer employed. And with the strong performance of computers in the past ten years, this has indeed ceased –in most cases– to be a limitation.

Moreover, the synchronisation between the performer (or performer) ¹⁴ and the electronics in these compositions is achieved with extreme simplicity by following a SMPTE display on the stage showing a precise time-code which is written periodically in the score every time DSP functions are automatically activated. As a result, much more demanding activities on stage such as, for example, activating pedals or the usage of click-tracks with headphones (and the usual leakage of sound that accompanies it) can be simply avoided.

The benefits for both the musical performance and the staging of these pieces are evident, as less attention can be dedicated to the synchronisation of several DSP events and nevertheless, those DSP functions can be played with extreme accuracy in real time without the need of further requirements or activities. In this manner, performers can focus much more (or exclusively) on the musical aspects of the pieces and much less (or not at all) on those technological aspects, therefore, enhancing the chances of a satisfactory delivery of the intended dramaturgy and an optimum result for the output of the algorithms utilised in the electronics.

The paper also demonstrates with diverse examples, that the dramaturgy intended in the pieces depends strongly on the absolute accuracy of the electronic processes, and therefore, these pieces cannot be performed as intended without a full automation of their electronics. Said in other words, as Landy remarks in *Understanding the Art of Sound Organization* [4], Molino's approaches to analysis, the *poiesis* (related to the construction of the work) and the *aesthesis* (related to the reception of the piece) cannot be completely fulfilled with regard to these two compositions if any other type of electronic activation were to be used.

Intersections (memories) had its premiere at the 18th (and last) Annual Florida Electroacoustic Music Festival (University of Florida, USA) in April 2008¹⁵. *Confluences (Rainbows II)* was premiered in September 2012 in Ljubljana, Slovenia during the ICMC 2012.¹⁶

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¹⁴ Or even conductors, as in the case of the premiere of *Confluences*

¹⁵ The clarinet part was played by Jorge Variego.

¹⁶ The premiere was performed by: Anja Brezavšček (flute, Slovenia); Matjaž Porovne (violin, Slovenia); Jože Kotar (clarinet, Slovenia); Milan Hudnik (cello, Slovenia); Nina Prešiček (piano, Slovenia); Steven Loy (conductor, USA).